

**THEME: PAYING ATTENTION AND PROBLEMS OF CHILDREN'S
PRONUNCIATION IN TEACHING ENGLISH IN PRESCHOOL
EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS**

**ТЕМА: ПРОБЛЕМА ДЕТЕЙ И ПРОБЛЕМЫ В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ
АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА В ДОШКОЛЬНЫХ УЧЕБНЫХ
ЗАВЕДЕНИЯХ**

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Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена теме "внимание и проблемы в произношении детей при обучении английскому языку в дошкольных учреждениях". В этой статье представлен ряд рекомендаций по изучению английского языка в дошкольных учреждениях. В них говорилось о том, в каком стиле объяснять английскую лексику, и как этот метод интересен и эффективен для них.

Annotation. This article is devoted to the topic "paying attention to the pronunciation of children in teaching English in preschool institutions and the problems in them". In this article, a number of recommendations on the study of English in preschool institutions are given. They were told about how to explain the

English lexicon in such a way, and about the fact that this method is interesting and effective for them.

Key words :

образование	education
учреждение	institution
произношение	pronunciation
проблемы	problems
воспитатель	tutor
интересный	interesting
результативный	effective
совет	recommendation

We know that today the head of any state pays great attention to preschool education. Alternatively, It is important to teach foreign languages to children in English and Russian at elementary level before they go to school. Therefore, in a few articles, I would like to share some information on teaching children the simplest and most understandable English language. We know that children from 3 to 6 years old study in kindergarten. Of these, 5-6 years old are taught foreign languages at elementary level. Groups are given 20-30 minutes twice a week. Such classes last 68 hours a year. So in these 20 minutes, we need to be able to deliver the topic to the kids in English, to get them interested, and to be quick to say "yes" when the group tutor says in English.

How do we explain a second language to children? We teach them inseparably from the first language. For example, we put a picture or the original of the object we are teaching and ask the children questions to find out who knows it in first language. For example, if we give the example of carrot in theme "*vegetables*", we will ask the following questions:

- dear kids, Did everyone see carrots?
- what do we do with carrots?
- does everyone love it?

- what color is it?
- how do we feel when we eat it?
- where does it grow?

We ask children those questions in their first language. Children should be able to sit freely and enter roles to express their opinions. At the same time, we need to focus on each child and help them to be active and think. We say the word "carrot" in English together with children. When teaching English, we must first pay attention to pronunciation, because the word that children first learn will remain the same as they learned. An example of this is that we teach children to count when they go to 1st grade, but they may have learned it in kindergarten, or some children who walk in a house may have also learned to count from their siblings. For example, they learn the number *eight* 8 they may pronounce it as [eɪtʃ] like the letter Hh in kindergarten or from siblings and they may count: *one, two, three, four ... eight* [eɪtʃ], nine, ten. Elementary English teachers have a hard time explaining that we say [eɪt] and not [eɪtʃ] to say the number 8, and that if we say [eɪtʃ], we will say the letter Hh in the alphabet. They will fix this over the years. But the number 8 is called eight [eɪt]. The letter Hh [eɪtʃ] is the eighth letter of the alphabet. So we have to adapt the children's language without breaking the most rude mispronunciation. I will also give another example: the letter "Rr" in the English alphabet is pronounced as "r" when it comes at the beginning of a word, if it comes in the middle or at the end of a word, "r" is not pronounced, for example: in the word *rain* [reɪn] the letter "r" must be pronounced, but in the word *there* or *pair* the letter "r" must not be pronounced. That is why we must first pay attention to the pronunciation of children when teaching English.

We also ask the word *carrot* together with children, and then we ask each child individually, over and over again, and then the children draw a picture of the carrot in their notebooks and paint it and say yellow carrot, red carrot.

Thus, We have to conduct the lessons by speaking in English with the English phrases used in the classroom. We teach four poems on the topic covered in each lesson - for example, 68 poems in 68 lessons. This has a strong effect not only on

the student's ability to read English at school but also with excellent grades to listen to and understand simple texts, as well as to develop the ability to read.

To do this, The tutor who teaches English at the preschool must have all the equipment needed in the classroom to conduct the lessons. For example, pictures of the topic, the original, the computer, the incentives given to the student, and so on. At First lesson of full lessons given:

Lesson -1

Greeting (English prases)

Hello- goodmorning-
Good-bye- sit down-
Stand up- what is your name?-
My name is...-

By showing a picture of these new words, we repeat them together with children and ensure that the children do them separately and listen and understand from the computer. We will also show a cartoon or roller coaster for children featuring these words and teach poetry.

Goodmorning , goodmorning
Goodmorning to you
Goodmorning , goodmorning
I am glad to see you.

We return the poem together with the children and return it to each child separately and write it on a small piece of paper for each of the children and send it home with them. We tell them that when they come home, they should study with your parents or siblings, memorize, and we can finish the lesson and say goodbye to the kids. GOOD-BYE MY DEAR.

At Lesson 2:

Lesson-2

Colours

White- blue-

<i>Yellow-</i>	<i>green-</i>
<i>Brown-</i>	<i>red-</i>
<i>Orange-</i>	<i>pink-</i>
<i>Grey-</i>	<i>black-</i>

In doing so, we exhibit colors that children can distinguish from each other and ask how much they know about colors in their pure mother tongue. We show different objects and ask for their colors in their native language, for example, we show a picture of a rainbow, we teach each of the colors over and over again to the children. In this process we get each child to pronounce colours correctly with a great of attention, and then ask the children to color the rainbow in their notebooks with colored pencils. We listen to a song about colors from the computer. The children sing together, and then we recite the poem from Lesson 2.

Rain,rain go away
Come again another day
Little Tommy wants to play
Rain,rain go away.

At lesson 3:

Lesson-3

Revision

Here we repeat the 2 lessons learned. In 20 minutes we have to deliver 2 lessons to the kids previously learned. We work separately with low-achieving kids to determine how well they know. The children repeat the theme of "*greeting*" and "*colors*" in the previous lesson, recite the poems and perform the theme of greeting. We should give incentives to the children in different ways and in each exercise, so that incentives we give may reach their homes.

In this way, if we have a great number of large units, we can grind, simplify them and teach children easily to understand. We show all the lessons through

games, through cartoons on the computer, and sing interesting songs. Together with the children we prepare rollers and practice them in a sitting position.

In summary, in preschool educational institutions children just as the children who went to school can learn the basics of reading, writing, saying numbers, and so on in English language like their first language. They can also say colours of an object and build their primary opinion about something in English language. They can also have an idea of what they know in English and, most importantly, be able to pronounce English without difficulty when they go to school.

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